

Impact of GABA_A and GABA_B inhibition on cortical dynamics and perturbational complexity during synchronous and asynchronous activity

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ABSTRACT

Quantitative estimations of cortical complexity are used in the clinic as a measure of consciousness levels, but the cortical mechanisms involved are poorly understood. We used a version of the Perturbational Complexity Index adapted to the cerebral cortex *in vitro* (sPCI) to investigate the role of gabaergic inhibition in cortical complexity. We studied two dynamical states: slow-wave activity and “awake-like” activity, which express low and high causal complexity respectively. Progressive blockade of GABAergic inhibition during both regimes revealed its impact on emergent cortical activity and on sPCI. Gradual GABA_A-Rs blockade resulted in higher synchronization and progressively reduced sPCI. Blocking GABA_B-Rs also resulted in a reduced sPCI while in slow-waves. Our findings demonstrate that physiological levels of inhibition contribute to generation of dynamical richness and cortical complexity. However, if inhibition is diminished or enhanced, cortical complexity decreases. Using a computational model we demonstrate a link between excitatory/inhibitory balance and cortical complexity.

Keywords

cortical complexity; cortical slices; slow oscillations; slow waves; Up states

Introduction

Brain dynamics vary according to different brain states, resulting in different spontaneous spatiotemporal patterns of activity, functional connectivity, responsiveness to stimuli, behavior and cognition. Consequently, the same cells and networks allow a variety of states, amplifying the functional repertoire of a single system. These states can be physiological (e.g., awake, slow wave sleep, REM), drug-induced (e.g., anesthesia), or even different attentional states or variations within the awake state (McCormick et al., 2020). Brain states can also be pathological, like the so-called disorders of consciousness that can follow traumatic brain injury or stroke (for a review, see Giacino et al. 2014). Different brain states are also associated with different consciousness levels. For example, slow wave sleep, deep anesthesia or comatose states are associated with unconsciousness, while the awake state is a conscious state. Having measures that capture consciousness levels, or rather, the associated brain state, is particularly relevant in the clinical realm, in particular when consciousness levels are pathologically altered. An unresponsive patient may eventually be conscious, and it is critical to provide adequate tools for communication. Or it is important to have measures to determine whether an anesthetized patient is not only unresponsive, but unconscious. One of the parameters that has been proposed as a signature of the level of consciousness is brain complexity (Tononi & Edelman, 1998).

Network complexity represents the relationship between different components of the system, and the study of complexity is currently an active field across many disciplines. In particular, when applied to the brain, there is a variety of measures that try to capture brain complexity. Some measures focus on temporal complexity, others on topological complexity, or in spatiotemporal complexity of spontaneous activity measured by means of either brain imaging or electrophysiology (Bettinardi et al., 2015; Bullmore & Sporns, 2009; Tononi & Edelman, 1998; Tononi et al., 1994). A variety of measures include Lempel–Ziv compressibility (Hudetz et al., 2016; Szczepański et al., 2003), Shannon entropy (Zhao et al., 2010), entropy of wave propagation (Barbero-Castillo et al., 2019) and functional complexity (Zamora-López et al., 2016), amongst others. While comparing complexity after propofol sedation, Varley et al. (2020) report that various complexity measures are able to discriminate between levels of sedation, with temporal measures showing higher sensitivity. Another approach to quantifying cortical complexity is not to focus on spontaneous activity, but instead to induce a perturbation of

the system in order to investigate the causal interactions that follow. A measure that was proposed was the Perturbational Complexity Index (PCI) (Casali et al., 2013; Comolatti et al., 2019) in which neural activity is exogenously perturbed by means of stimulation (transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) or electrical stimulation). This method has been validated for different instances such as physiological brain states (Casali et al., 2013), anesthesia levels (Arena et al., 2020; Dasilva et al., in review; Sarasso et al., 2015) and disorders of consciousness (Casarotto et al., 2016).

The use of PCI in humans shows that cortical bistability, which is typical of a highly synchronized state such as slow wave sleep, is a regime of low complexity. Bistability prevents the cortical network engaging in a chain of complex causal interactions that are typical of the awake state (Massimini et al., 2005, 2007; Pigorini et al., 2015). In such “bistable” states, the network falls into an “off-period” following stimulation (Rosanova et al., 2018). At the other extreme, the awake, conscious state, is one of high complexity. In between high and low complexity states, there are intermediate brain states and intermediate complexity levels, that can be investigated using various anesthetics (Sarasso et al., 2015), at different levels of anesthesia (Dasilva et al.; in review) or in different disorders of consciousness (Casarotto et al., 2016). In order to explore the underlying cellular and network mechanisms behind cortical complexity, D’Andola et al. adapted the PCI measure to *in vitro* slice experiments, known as slice PCI (sPCI) (D’Andola et al., 2017). They showed that when the local network switched from a slow oscillatory state to an “awake-like” state induced by norepinephrine and carbachol, the bistability of Up/Down states was reduced and there was an increase in sPCI. In this way, the isolated cortical network *in vitro* was validated as a system which can not only spontaneously generate slow oscillations (Sanchez-Vives & McCormick, 2000) and mimic other brain states (Markram et al., 2015), but can also be used to investigate the cellular mechanisms of cortical complexity (D’Andola et al., 2017). In such local networks, one can specifically activate or inactivate ion/metabotropic receptors to induce changes in the spontaneous or evoked activity (sPCI) and provide insights about the underlying mechanisms controlling the transition across cortical states and potential associated changes in network complexity.

A fundamental property of cortical processing is the co-occurrence of excitation and inhibition not only in response to sensory stimulation but also during spontaneous cortical activity (Isaacson & Scanziani, 2011). In order to shed light on the role of inhibition in cortical complexity, here we combined electrophysiological recordings and

computational simulations to investigate the relevance of fast inhibition, mediated by GABA_A receptors (GABA_A-Rs), and slow inhibition, mediated by GABA_B receptors (GABA_B-Rs). We first investigated the transformation of spontaneous activity patterns while gradually blocking each of these receptors. Next, we tested the ability of the cortical network to engage in complex patterns of casual interactions. To obtain a better understanding, we did this under two different dynamical patterns corresponding to sleep and awake states: (1) during a bistable state, characterized by the presence of slow oscillations, and (2) during an “awake-like” state, in which neuronal bistability was reduced. We found that blockade of both GABA_A and GABA_B receptors in cortical slices generally reduced cortical complexity. Finally, we reproduced the experimental observations in a biologically inspired computational model (based on Compte et al. 2003) and demonstrate dependence of complexity on the excitatory/inhibitory balance. Interestingly, physiological levels of inhibition are optimal for reaching maximum complexity, while an excess or lack of inhibition results in a decreased sPCI.

Results

Synchronous vs awake-like states in the cortical network: spontaneous activity and perturbational complexity

In vitro extracellular 16-channel local field potentials (LFPs) were recorded from ferret primary visual cortex (V1) coronal slices ($n=58$) during two different regimes of spontaneous activity: (i) synchronous activity consisting in spontaneous Up and Down states organized in slow oscillations (SO) (Figures 1A and 2A–C), and (ii) asynchronous, “awake-like” activity (Figure 2A–C).

Figure 1. Experimental set up **A. Top** - We recorded activity with 16-channel multi-electrode array (MEA) from neocortical slices. Single pulses of electrical stimulation were applied to the infragranular layers (red arrow). **Bottom** - Representative local field potential (LFP) traces. **B.** Network complexity (Perturbational Complexity Index in slice, sPCI) was calculated using Lempel-Ziv compression of the significant multiunit activity ($SS(x,t)$) contained in a binary matrix. **C.** Summary plot of the sPCI calculated in control slices by applying different pulse amplitudes to the slices ($n=9$). **D.** Population average of the sPCI calculated in control slices with a varying number of stimulation pulses. Blue range was used during complexity protocols ($n=9$).

Figure 2. Network complexity increased from spontaneous synchronous slow oscillation to ‘awake-like’ activity. **A.** Raw LFP (top) and MUA (bottom) recordings of 5 s of spontaneous slow oscillation (left), “NE+CCh” (middle) and “awake-like” activity (right). **B.** Representative autocorrelograms showing the lack of slow oscillatory activity during “awake-like” activity (right). **C.** Spectrograms of spontaneous activity from LFP recordings shown in A. **D.** Averaged LFP (top) and MUA (bottom) responses to electrical stimulation during spontaneous slow oscillation (left), “NE+CCh” (middle) and “awake-like” activity (right). Binary matrices of significant sources of activity ($SS(x,t)$) following a single electrical pulse delivered to neocortical slices (bottom) (left). Population sPCI measured during control slow oscillation, “NE+CCh” and “awake-like” activity (right). (** p -value<0.01)

In our experimental paradigm, cortical slices displayed spontaneous slow oscillations similar to the ones occurring *in vivo* during slow wave sleep (Sanchez-Vives & McCormick, 2000). Oscillatory frequencies in the different slices ranged from 0.2 to 0.92 Hz (mean 0.47 ± 0.02 Hz, $n=58$). While the synchronous slow oscillatory state replicates the dynamics of slow wave sleep, asynchronous activity in the slice can mimic that of awake states. In cortical slices, asynchronous or nearly-asynchronous states can be mimicked by adding up neurotransmitters, through bath application of norepinephrine (NE) and acetylcholine (ACh), present in awake states (Brumberg et al., 2000; D’Andola et al., 2017; Jones, 2005; McCormick, 1992). Even when cholinergic and noradrenergic

agonists block slow oscillations, there is synchronization at a higher frequency of ~ 2.4 Hz (see Figure 2A,B). In order to obtain a more asynchronous activity, we used additional strategies based on previous studies, which further desynchronized the network (see Methods; Figure 2A–C). Using a measure of complexity of time series called Sample Entropy (SampEn, see Methods), we quantified the level of regularity of the signal during three different types of spontaneous activity or conditions that we will use along the study: (1) slow oscillations, (2) “CCh+NE” to refer to the presence of cholinergic (carbachol) and noradrenergic (norepinephrine) agonists in the bath and, (3) “awake-like” activity (see Methods for details). The mean SampEn was significantly different in all of them (control: 0.751 ± 0.027 ; CCh+NE: 0.868 ± 0.033 ; awake-like: 0.906 ± 0.035 ; $F(2,38)=13.087$, $p=4.742 \times 10^{-5}$, $n=20$). In particular, SampEn measured during “CCh+NE” and “awake-like” activity was significantly higher than during SO (CCh+NE: $t_{(38)}=5.218$, $p=0.002$; awake-like: $t_{(38)}=6.95$, $p=5.07 \times 10^{-5}$, $n=20$), as we would expect given that SO are more synchronized states.

In order to quantify the complexity of network responses to single pulse electrical stimulation, we used an adapted version of the PCI (Casali et al., 2013) for slice recordings (sPCI; Figure 1B; see Methods) (D’Andola et al., 2017). During ongoing slow oscillations, electrical stimulation evoked a response followed by a sudden decrease in activity, Down state or what has been referred in humans to as “off-periods” (Rosanova et al., 2018), resembling reported findings for LFP recordings in humans (Pigorini et al., 2015; Rosanova et al., 2018). According to the sPCI algorithm by (D’Andola et al., 2017) and in order to quantify the spatiotemporal patterns of response to electrical stimulation, we converted the raw LFP traces obtained from multielectrode array recordings to firing rate signals (specifically to logMUA, see Methods; Figure 1B) and computed the binary matrices of significant activity (Figure 1B; for details see Methods). We then compressed the spatiotemporal binary matrices of significant sources with a Lempel–Ziv algorithm, and normalized them by the source entropy to finally obtain the sPCI. Under synchronous, slow oscillatory activity, the sPCI was 0.1 ± 0.002 (range 0.07–0.14, $n=58$), similar to what has been previously reported (D’Andola et al., 2017; Dasilva et al., in review).

We tested the reliability of the sPCI in a subset of slices by (i) applying different stimulation intensities (Figure 1C) and (ii) increasing the number of stimuli repetitions (Figure 1D). The population sPCI did not vary significantly when different stimulation intensities were applied within the range of 50 to 300 μ A (Table S1; $n=9$; Figure 1C). However, the sPCI was slightly dependent on the number of stimulation trials. For 15

repetitions this was 0.092 ± 0.004 , 0.083 ± 0.004 for 30 repetitions, 0.085 ± 0.003 for 60 repetitions, and 0.084 ± 0.004 for 100 repetitions ($F_{(3,24)}=4.44$, $p=0.012$, $n=9$; Figure 1D). The sPCI significantly decreased above 15 repetitions but remained stable for 30, 60, and 100 repetitions (15 vs 30 rep.: $t_{(24)}=2.66$, $p=0.261$; 15 vs 60 rep.: $t_{(24)}=4.34$, $p=0.025$; 15 vs 100 rep.: $t_{(24)}=4.57$, $p=0.017$; 30 vs 60 rep.: $t_{(24)}=1.67$, $p=0.644$; 30 vs 100 rep.: $t_{(24)}=1.91$, $p=0.541$; 60 vs 100 rep.: $t_{(24)}=0.24$, $p=0.998$; $n=9$; Figure 1D). Therefore, in the rest of the study we consistently calculated PCI with 40 as the number of stimuli.

sPCI in different dynamic regimes of cortical activity

We next calculated sPCI in the three described conditions: (1) slow oscillations, (2) “CCh+NE” and, (3) “awake-like”, asynchronous state. As said above, following the bath application of CCh+NE, network bistability of Up/Down states was blocked (Figure 2A–C), the network went on to generate a higher frequency (~ 2.4 Hz) of smaller amplitude, with an increased Sample Entropy. The sPCI following the electrical stimulation revealed a significant increase of the sPCI with respect to that in slow oscillations (Figure 2D), similar to what was reported previously (D’Andola et al., 2017). In the “awake-like”, asynchronous state, the mean sPCI was also significantly larger than that in slow oscillations, but not higher than in “NE+CCh”, in spite of being more asynchronous and with a higher Sample Entropy than the former (Control: 0.103 ± 0.004 ; awake-like: 0.141 ± 0.005 , $t_{(38)}=8.599$, $p=1.301 \times 10^{-6}$, $n=20$; Figure 2D). Therefore, when cortical complexity was calculated by means of sPCI, there was a significant increase in complexity following the blockade of network Up/Down state bistability, which is a highly synchronous state. However, the more subtle change in dynamics taking place between conditions “NE+CCh” and “awake-like” did not convey a complexity increase as detected by sPCI. From this point on in the study, we used two departing points or baselines that we compared: (1) slow oscillatory, synchronous state, and (2) “awake-like”, asynchronous state. These two extremes of the dynamics mimic awake *versus* slow wave sleep, or awake *versus* deep anesthesia, respectively.

Role of GABA_A receptors on the modulation of cortical dynamics and complexity: blocking of GABA_A receptors in the “awake-like” state

To investigate the GABAergic role in cortical complexity we explored how a progressive blockade of inhibition affected sPCI while departing from two different dynamic states, either (1) asynchronous, “awake-like” state or, (2) synchronous, slow

oscillatory state. We first induced the “awake-like” state (Figure 3A) as described in the Methods, and next we blocked fast inhibition by application of the selective GABA_A receptor blocker gabazine (Figure 3; 50–200 nM). When GABA_A receptors were blocked, “awake-like” dynamics progressively shifted towards pre-epileptiform dynamics (Figure 3A,B) as described in (Sanchez-Vives et al. 2010; fig. 6D). We illustrate how this effect was expressed in the raw traces (Figure 3A) and in the spectrogram of the activity (Figure 3B). Such modification of spontaneous dynamics was also reflected in the spatiotemporal pattern of responses to perturbation (Figure 3C), that were used for the calculation of sPCI (Figure 3C–E). As shown above, from slow oscillatory regime to “awake-like” regime, there was an increase in sPCI. However, following the maximum sPCI reached in the “awake-like” state, the progressive blockade of GABA_A receptors resulted in a progressive decline of sPCI (Table S2, $n=10$; Figure 3D–E). Interestingly, whereas the sPCI was significantly reduced compared to the “awake-like” state for concentrations above 50 nM gabazine (GBZ 100 nM: $t_{(45)}=5.56$, $p=0.003$; GBZ 150 nM: $t_{(45)}=6.979$, $p=1.588\times 10^{-4}$; GBZ200 nM: $t_{(45)}=10.485$, $p=4.128\times 10^{-8}$; $n=10$; Figure 3D), it was only at the highest concentration of gabazine that the sPCI significantly decayed below control levels ($t_{(45)}=6.294$, $p=7.525\times 10^{-4}$, $n=10$; Figure 3D). The trend showed in Figure 3E was in agreement with the temporal evolution of the sPCI (Figure 3D) that showed a faster increase in the awake-like state with respect to the other two conditions in which the increase of sPCI reached a plateau around 0.6s after the stimulation. In summary, these results indicate that blockade of GABA_A receptors in the “awake-like” state decreases perturbational complexity in cortical slices, or conversely, physiological GABA_A-mediated inhibition contributes to cortical complexity during asynchronous dynamics. Further, highly synchronous epileptiform discharges (in 200 nM gabazine) display decreased complexity, as seen in humans (Massimini et al., 2007).

Figure 3. Progressive blockade of GABA_A receptors reduces sPCI during awake-like activity recovering bistability. **A** Raw LFP recordings of spontaneous activity in neocortical slices, during slow oscillation, “awake-like” activity and blockade of GABA_A receptors by bath application of increasing concentrations of GBZ demonstrated progressively shifted towards pre-epileptiform dynamics. **B.** Spectrograms of spontaneous activity from LFP recordings shown in A. **C.** Averaged LFP (top) and MUA (middle) to electrical stimulation during distinct regimes of activity. Binary matrices of significant sources of activity ($SS(x,t)$) following a single electrical pulse delivered to neocortical slices (bottom). **D.** Time evolution of sPCI in the three experimental conditions **E.** Population sPCI demonstrated that presence of large Down-states breaks the causal interactions and decreased the complexity of the responses. (* p -value<0.05).

Role of GABA_A receptors in the modulation of cortical dynamics and complexity: blocking of GABA_A receptors in the slow oscillatory state

We next investigated the effect of GABA_A receptors-blockade on complexity but departing from slow oscillations. We bath-applied increasing concentrations of bicuculline methiodide (BMI; 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1 μ M) and recorded network responses to electrical stimulation. Raising BMI concentrations induced a gradual

shortening of evoked Up states and augmented Up-state amplitude (Figure 4A), as previously described (Sanchez-Vives et al., 2010). Such an increase in Up-state amplitude corresponded to a linear increase in the firing rate during Up states with the removal of inhibition (Figure 4B) due to an enhanced excitatory reverberation. The increase in firing rate was significant for all conditions compared to slow oscillations (Table S3, $n=9$; Figure 4C) (BMI 0.2 μM : $t_{(40)}=5.25$, $p=0.008$; BMI 0.4 μM : $t_{(40)}=9.96$, $p=2.87\times 10^{-7}$; BMI 0.6 μM : $t_{(40)}=14.98$, $p=2.21\times 10^{-10}$; BMI 0.8 μM : $t_{(40)}=18.15$, $p<0.001$; BMI 1 μM : $t_{(40)}=19.83$, $p<0.001$). Up states of larger amplitude resulted in binary matrices with shorter significant periods of activity (Figure 4C,D). In particular, bath-application of BMI reduced the sPCI with respect to slow oscillations (Table S2; $n=9$; Figure 4E). Post-hoc analysis revealed that the trend of decay of sPCI with the removal of fast inhibition became significantly reduced at 1 μM BMI with respect to slow oscillations ($t_{(40)}=4.93$, $p=0.014$, $n=9$).

Figure 4. Progressive blockade of GABA_A receptors reduces sPCI during SWA.

A. Raw LFP recordings of spontaneous activity in neocortical slices, control slow oscillations and blockade of GABA_A receptors by bath application of increasing concentrations of gabazine induced shortening of

evoked Up states. **B.** Spectrograms of the spontaneous activity shown in A. **C.** Population FRs for increasing GBZ concentrations. **D.** Averaged LFP (top) and MUA (middle) responses to electrical stimulation during distinct regimes of activity. Bottom, binary matrices of significant sources of activity ($SS(x,t)$) following a single electrical pulse delivered to neocortical slices. **E.** Time evolution of sPCI in the three experimental conditions **F.** Population sPCI demonstrated that presence of large Down-states breaks the causal interactions and correlates with low complexity states

BMI is known to block additional targets such as the small conductance calcium activated potassium (SK) channels (Khawaled et al., 1999). To avoid potential confounding effects in our experiments, we next bath-applied increasing concentrations of gabazine, a specific blocker of GABA_A that lacks the effect on SK channels. Blockade of GABA_A-Rs by increasing concentrations of gabazine also induced shortening of evoked Up states (Figure 4A,B), as previously shown (Sanchez-Vives et al., 2010). As occurred after application of BMI, the firing rate during Up states also gradually increased, eventually leading to epileptiform discharges in some cases (Table S3, $n=9$; Figure 4B). Although the firing rate increase showed a clear trend for all gabazine concentrations, this increase was significant above 50 nM (GBZ 50 nM: $t_{(32)}=1.43$, $p=0.85$; GBZ 100 nM: $t_{(32)}=5.07$, $p=0.009$; GBZ 150 nM: $t_{(32)}=10.17$, $p=3.43\times 10^{-7}$; GBZ 200 nM: $t_{(32)}=10.01$, $p=4.7\times 10^{-7}$; $n=9$) (Figure 4C).

The change in sPCI induced by the removal of fast inhibition with gabazine was largely similar to the one induced by BMI. Overall, the sPCI significantly decreased with increasing gabazine concentrations (Table S2, $n=9$; Figure 4D–F). In particular, the sPCI reduction with respect to the slow oscillations condition was significant above 50 nM gabazine (GBZ 150 nM: $t_{(32)}=7.04$, $p=1.94\times 10^{-4}$; GBZ 200 nM: $t_{(32)}=7.22$, $p=1.36\times 10^{-4}$; $n=9$).

Thus, these results indicate that removal of fast inhibition reduces perturbational complexity in cortical slices. Enhanced excitability during Up states due to excitatory recurrency in cortical circuits induced stereotypical responses to stimulation that resulted in lower sPCI values. Balanced GABA_A-R mediated inhibition in cortical activity provides richness in the emergent patterns, contributing to the complexity of causal interactions. In our computer model below, we explored the limits of the relationship between inhibition and complexity, in a range that is unattainable experimentally.

Role of GABA_B receptors in the modulation of cortical dynamics and complexity: blocking of GABA_B receptors in the awake-like state

Next, we followed a similar approach to investigate the effects of progressive GABA_B receptor blockade during awake-like activity in cortical slices. Departing from slow oscillatory spontaneous activity, we induced awake-like activity. The transformation of the activity is illustrated in the raw recordings (Figure 5A) and in the spectrogram (Figure 5B). We then bath-applied increasing concentrations of CGP55845, a specific antagonist of GABA_B receptors. Such application had a progressive effect enhancing the synchronization in the network (Figure 5A,B) although it did not turn activity into epileptiform activity as GABA_A-R blockade did (Figure 3A,B). We computed the sPCI for each condition (Figure 5C) and significant differences were found ($F_{(5,30)}=2.921$, $p=0.029$; Table S4, $n=7$; Figure 5C–E). Although sPCI significantly increased during “awake-like” condition compared to SO ($t_{(30)}=4.75$, $p=0.024$, $n=7$), post-hoc tests did not reveal significant differences, neither between control vs CGP conditions (CGP 100 nM: $t_{(30)}=2.87$, $p=0.348$; CGP 200 nM: $t_{(30)}=1.68$, $p=0.837$; CGP 500 nM: $t_{(30)}=1.29$, $p=0.941$; CGP 1 μ M: $t_{(30)}=0.69$, $p=0.996$; $n=7$) nor “awake-like” vs CGP groups (CGP 100 nM: $t_{(30)}=1.88$, $p=0.768$; CGP 200 nM: $t_{(30)}=3.07$, $p=0.281$; CGP 500 nM: $t_{(30)}=3.47$, $p=0.171$; CGP 1 μ M: $t_{(30)}=4.07$, $p=0.072$; $n=7$). The temporal evolution of sPCI also revealed an increase in the “awake-like” condition, but a similar evolution in slow oscillations and under GABA_B-Rs blockade, conditions with an increased synchronization and thus lesser spatiotemporal richness in the patterns. In summary, these results indicate that blockade of GABA_B receptors during awake-like activity showed a trend towards a decreased sPCI but did not reach significance. Thus, the contribution of GABA_B-mediated inhibition to causal complexity in the awake state is less relevant than that of GABA_A-mediated inhibition.

Figure 5. Progressive blockade of GABA_B receptors did not significantly reduce the sPCI during awake-like activity.

A. Raw LFP recordings of spontaneous activity in neocortical slices slow oscillations, “awake-like” activity and blockade of GABA_B receptors by bath application of increasing concentrations of CGP, which enhanced the synchronization in the network. **B.** Spectrograms of spontaneous activity from LFP recordings shown in A. **C.** Averaged LFP (top) and MUA (middle) to electrical stimulation during distinct regimes of activity. Binary matrices of significant sources of activity ($SS(x,t)$) following a single electrical pulse delivered to neocortical slices (bottom). **D.** Time evolution of sPCI in the three experimental conditions **E.** Population sPCI demonstrated that higher synchronization reduces cortical complexity.

Role of GABA_B receptors in the modulation of cortical dynamics and complexity: blocking of GABA_B receptors in the slow oscillatory state

During slow oscillations, GABA_B receptors have been found to play a role in Up-state termination since their blockade results in longer persistent activity (Mann et al., 2009; Perez-Zabalza et al., 2020; Sanchez-Vives et al., 2020). In order to further investigate the role of GABA_B-Rs mediated inhibition in emergent activity and cortical complexity, we gradually blocked GABA_B receptors while departing from slow

oscillatory activity. Progressive blockade of GABA_B-Rs induced Up states of longer duration followed by prominent Down states that decreased the frequency of Up states and increased their regularity, as described in Perez-Zabalza et al. (2020) (Figure 6A,B). The spectrograms illustrate the enhanced synchronization. The sPCI decreased following GABA_B receptor blockade ($F_{(4,40)}=9.351$, $p=1.97\times 10^{-5}$; Table S4, $n=11$; Figure 6D–F). The time evolution of sPCI (Figure 6E) also decreased with GABA_B receptor blockade. Significant sPCI reductions were confirmed by post-hoc analysis for the three tested conditions (CGP 200 nM: $t_{(40)}=5.38$, $p=0.004$; CGP 500 nM: $t_{(40)}=5.87$, $p=0.002$; CGP 1 μ M: $t_{(40)}=7.98$, $p=1.45\times 10^{-5}$; $n=11$). Interestingly, the removal of slow inhibition by bath-application of increasing concentrations of CGP55845 significantly increased the firing rate during Up states ($F_{(1.84,18.42)}=4.481$, $p=0.028$; Table S5, $n=11$; Figure 6C), although to a less extent than GABA_A receptor blockade did. Only bath-application of 1 μ M CGP55845 resulted in a significant increase of firing rate ($t_{(40)}=4.996$, $p=0.009$, $n=11$). Finally, we showed that blockade of GABA_B-Rs, while in slow oscillations, reduced perturbational complexity, confirming that GABA_B-Rs mediated-inhibition contribute to the richness of activity patterns, spatiotemporal variability and cortical complexity during the slow oscillatory regime.

Figure 6. Progressive blockade of GABA_B receptors reduces sPCI during SO leading stereotypical activity. **A.** Raw LFP recordings of spontaneous activity in neocortical slices, control slow oscillations and blocking GABA_B receptors by bath application of increasing concentrations of CGP, which induced Up states of longer duration followed by prominent Down states, decreasing the Up-state frequency and increasing the regularity. **B.** Spectrograms of spontaneous activity from LFP recordings shown in **A**. **C.** Population of relative FRs of increasing concentrations of CGP. **D.** Averaged LFP (top) and MUA (middle) to electrical stimulation during distinct regimes of activity. Binary matrices of significant sources of activity ($SS(x,t)$) following a single electrical pulse delivered to neocortical slices (bottom). **E.** Time evolution of sPCI in the three experimental conditions. **F.** Population sPCI. (* p -value < 0.05).

Cortical GABA_A and GABA_B receptors role in the modulation of cortical complexity in a cortical network model

In order to further investigate the cellular and network mechanisms involved in cortical network complexity, we implemented a modified version of a biophysically detailed neuronal model (Compte et al., 2003) in a two-dimensional network, in order to explore spatiotemporal dynamics of spontaneous and induced cortical complexity. The

model consists of pyramidal and inhibitory conductance-based neurons synaptically connected within a local range. Pyramidal cells have a larger range of connectivity than inhibitory neurons, which are more locally connected (Figure 7A, see Methods for details). Our neuronal model includes GABA_A as in Compte et al. (2003) and additionally accounts for GABA_B inhibitory synapses as well as potassium leakage current which is modulated by acetylcholine (ACh) and NE (Bazhenov et al., 2002; Li et al., 2017). In this model, we simulated and recorded simulated population local field potentials (sLFP) from 12 different locations organized in a matrix (see Methods).

The sLFP signal was analyzed with exactly the same techniques as the ones experimentally recorded in the cortical slices. The model is able to reproduce slow oscillatory dynamics and “awake-like” activity as observed *in vitro*, as well as the cortical activity under blockade of GABA_A-Rs and GABA_B-Rs (Figure 7A,B; see video in Supplementary Materials). We then evaluated the perturbational complexity in the cortical network model. For slow oscillations and “awake-like” activity, the sPCI showed similar values to those observed *in vitro*: 0.0834 ± 0.0123 and 0.1434 ± 0.0103 , respectively. We next tested the effects of the progressive blockade of GABA_A and GABA_B during both different dynamics corresponding to the conditions of slow oscillations and “awake-like” states. The maximal effect of GABA_A blockade on the sPCI during slow oscillations occurred by reducing the receptor availability by 20%, when we obtained values of sPCI 0.0522 ± 0.0146 that remained unchanged for lower availability (Figure 7C, top-left). On the other hand, the sPCI during “awake-like” dynamics progressively decreased with the GABA_A-Rs blockade, reaching a plateau for blocks of more than 80% of receptors, 0.0876 ± 0.0058 , (Figure 7C, top-right). Interestingly, for large GABA_A blockade during “awake-like” activity, the sPCI values approach those observed during slow oscillations, as observed experimentally. For the GABA_B blockade, we observed a progressive slow decay of the sPCI values from SO conditions (Figure 7C, bottom-left), while for “awake-like” dynamics we did not observe any trend in sPCI (Figure 7C, bottom-right). To a lesser extent, the GABA_B effects were also similar to those observed experimentally. Since GABA_A presented a stronger effect on the perturbational complexity in both conditions (i.e., SO and “awake-like” dynamics), we next proceeded to evaluate the network dynamics in two scenarios: (1) in a disinhibited network, and (2) in an inhibited network. As observed experimentally during SO, when we blocked GABA_A, (i.e., disinhibited the network) the spontaneous activity presents a shorter Up

state with higher firing rate (e.g., compare Figure 7B top-left with top-middle-left). In the model, we observed that the dynamics of spontaneous activity in a disinhibited network during SO is fully integrated, while weakly segregated, giving rise to activation waves that rapidly span the whole network (Figure 8A, right. See video in Supplementary Materials). Conversely, when the network is inhibited, the spontaneous activity is highly segregated and weakly integrated, and the activation waves propagate more locally and do not span over the whole network (Figure 8A, left. See video in Supplementary Materials). Nonetheless, when there is a balance between integration and segregation, the activation waves span over the whole network recruiting their nearest neighbors (Figure 8A, middle. See video in Supplementary Materials). Finally, we evaluated the perturbational complexity networks where the inhibition was not only decreased (as in the experiments), but also increased. While departing from the slow oscillatory regime, we found that increasing inhibition by +20% further increased sPCI (0.1023 ± 0.0153), remaining high during SO for highly inhibited networks (+90%, 0.0878 ± 0.0162) (Figure 8B). The increment on the sPCI values for slightly more inhibited networks may be due to the fact that the neurons on the network fired less during the Up states, and therefore had less hyperpolarization at the beginning of Down states (Figure 8C), shortening the Down states and allowing a less synchronized and bistable network. These results suggest that there is a close link between integration and segregation with E/I balance, and that higher/lower sPCI values are not the consequence of merely increasing/decreasing excitability.

Figure 7. A network cortical model to reproduce the sPCI measured during different regimes of network activity. **A.** The model consists of pyramidal (blue) and inhibitory neurons (red) arranged in a 50x50 square lattice. The excitatory neurons may connect locally to a 50% fraction of its neighbours (grey circles) within a 7x7 square, while the inhibitory neurons to a 90% fraction within a 5x5 square (see Methods). **B.** The model reproduces similar spontaneous and evoked neuronal activity, as observed experimentally during (from left to right) slow oscillations, slow oscillations + blocking GABA_A, slow oscillations + blocking GABA_B and “awake-like” activity. Single spontaneous sLFP (top), averaged sLFP (middle top), MUA (middle bottom) and binary matrices of significant sources of activity (SS(x,t)) following a single electrical pulse delivered in a cortical model. **C.** Population sPCI for different cortical activity – slow oscillations (SO) with GABA_A (left-top) and GABA_B (left-bottom) progressively blockade, the same for awake-like activity (right column).

Figure 8. sPCI for an inhibited and disinhibited cortical network model. **A.** Example snapshot of cortical network activity for three networks with different inhibition (G_{A_A}) concentration (E/I balance). The color scale indicates the time since each neuron last spiked, thus illustrating the temporal dynamics of activity propagation. Right, networks with low inhibition blockage (-80%) show high integration, while, left, with high inhibition blockage (+80%) show high segregation (left). Middle, networks with an intermediate segregation/integration balance. See the simulations in the Supplementary Video. **B.** Population sPCI for inhibited and disinhibited cortical networks. The shadow area represents the model predictions. **C.** Membrane potential traces for three neurons in the cortical network model during slow oscillations (CTRL), disinhibited (orange), slightly inhibited (red) and high inhibited (blue) cortical network activity. Notice the increase and decrease afterhyperpolarization (AHP) following the up state for slightly inhibited and high inhibited neurons, respectively.

Discussion

In this study we have investigated the role of GABA_A-Rs and GABA_B-Rs mediated inhibition on cortical emergent activity and complexity, in particular on complexity measured by means of perturbing the network with stimulation. By doing this we have attempted to bridge a macroscale clinical measure (PCI), with the synaptic and cellular components of the local cortical circuits. We found that during physiological activity, both types of inhibition—fast and slow—contribute to the generation of richness of spatiotemporal activity patterns and cortical complexity, and the progressive blockade of fast or slow inhibition results in enhanced synchronization and breakdown of complexity. However, the contribution of GABA_A and GABA_B mediated inhibition is different in the “awake-like” and in the slow oscillatory regimes, and this is discussed below. In our computational model we explore areas of the parameter space that cannot be reached experimentally, more extensively exploring the relationship between excitatory and inhibitory balance, network dynamics and cortical complexity.

The Perturbational Complexity Index (Casali et al., 2013; Comolatti et al., 2019) is a measure of cortical complexity that has been used to quantify consciousness levels, in awake/sleep, in anesthesia (Hudetz, 2012; Sarasso et al., 2015) and in patients with disorders of consciousness (Casarotto et al., 2016; Rosanova et al., 2012). This measure consists in the perturbation of the brain network by means of cortical stimulation in order to engage the corticothalamocortical circuit in causal interactions, and then capturing the spatiotemporal properties of the response in an index that reflects cortical complexity. It is based on the hypothesis that for consciousness to occur, simultaneous integration and segregation of information in the network are needed, resulting in high complexity in the awake state (Tononi and Edelman, 1998). Network complexity can be measured by different means in the spontaneous activity, either electrophysiological or imaging signal, as mentioned in the Introduction. However, a perturbational approach presents advantages with respect to an observational one (based on spontaneous activity) because it is less affected by noise or isolated processes, and only assesses information generated through deterministic interactions, which also gives advantages that are useful clinically (Casali et al., 2013). Given that there is accumulated evidence that brain complexity is a relevant property that informs about the brain state and consciousness levels, we want to link this measure to the properties of cells and circuits, to understand how the different

mechanisms may sculpt the resulting complexity. This understanding is also important to eventually devise strategies to recover complexity in pathological situations.

In order to investigate how inhibition contributes to complexity, we resorted to the progressive blockade of GABAergic receptors. However, network complexity in humans has been found to be different in the synchronized, slow oscillatory state (low complexity) and in the awake state (high complexity) (see above). For this reason, we carried out the GABAergic blockade while departing from these two extreme conditions, to understand the different role GABAergic inhibition plays in both regimes. SO dynamics is a multiscale phenomenon which emerges in cortical circuits whenever there is physical or functional disconnection of the cortex, such as NREM sleep or anesthesia (Alkire et al., 2008; Chauvette et al., 2011; Massimini et al., 2004; Riedner et al., 2007; Sanchez-Vives & McCormick, 2000; Steriade et al., 1993). For this reason, SO has been suggested to represent the “default” pattern of activity of the cortical network (Sanchez-Vives & Mattia, 2014), which emerges even in the isolated cortical *tissue in vitro* (Sanchez-Vives & McCormick, 2000). From synchronized regimes of SO, neural activity can transition towards asynchronous states leading to variable, irregular and spatiotemporally complex cortical rhythms, in which neurons fire irregularly and nearly independently during the awake state (Andalman et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2009; Constantinople et al., 2011; Duarte et al., 2017; Poulet & Crochet, 2019; Steriade et al., 2001). The cellular substrate underlying the switch between SO and asynchronous activity is provided, among others, by ascending cholinergic and noradrenergic neuromodulatory connections arising from subcortical structures, such as the basal forebrain or locus coeruleus (Hobson & Pace-Schott, 2002; Jones, 2005; Scammell et al., 2017; Weber & Dan, 2016). Our preparation reproduced several features of these different dynamics. Bath-application of CCh+NE shifted SO to low frequency 1–5 Hz oscillations (Figure 2A–C) (as in D’Andola et al. 2017) which in part resemble the cortical activity observed during wakefulness. Further, we lowered the temperature by 2°C to 32°C, which we have demonstrated previously diminishes cortical synchronization (Reig et al., 2010). Further, we lowered $[Ca^{2+}]_o$ levels to those reported earlier in mice (0.8–0.9mM) (Markram et al., 2015) to induce asynchrony. Both manipulations resulted in larger asynchrony as illustrated in the autocorrelograms (Figure 2B) and spectrograms (Figure 2C). Both manipulations led to higher sPCI values (Figure 2D) as well as increased SampEn with respect to the SO regime, which is consistent with the idea of different cortical dynamics. Our experimental

model thus allows the study of transitions between different cortical dynamics, SO to asynchronous states.

Departing from SO as well as from “awake-like” activity, GABA_A receptor blockade resulted in Up states of higher amplitude and shorter duration than those observed in control conditions (Figure 3A,B and 4A,B). This property has been described (Sanchez-Vives et al., 2010), but only for the evolution of Up states in SO. Interestingly, when departing from asynchronous activity, it is also possible to induce rhythmicity in low frequencies by partially blocking GABA_A-Rs. It should be noticed that this is not epileptiform activity, although progressive inhibition would eventually lead to epileptiform discharges. Disinhibition causes higher firing rates that induces a hypersynchronization of the network, as we also find in our computer model simulations. In the simulations, the activation of potassium channels is critical to induction of the silent periods. Such hypersynchronization of the network results in a decrease in complexity.

GABA_B receptor blockade during SOs increased Up-state duration (Mann et al., 2009; Perez-Zabalza et al., 2020), resulting in highly regular oscillatory patterns and prominent bistable responses to electrical perturbation (Figure 6). This finding is revealing of the role of GABA_B-Rs in increasing richness of activity patterns and irregularity in the Up and Down states (Perez-Zabalza et al., 2020). This is also translated in a consistently decreased sPCI with GABA_B-Rs blockade. A different situation takes place when departing from the “awake-like” state. In this situation, the blockade of GABA_B-Rs tends to, but does not induce a bistable oscillatory regime, nor significantly decrease sPCI. These findings suggest that the role of GABA_B-Rs in the asynchronous state for introducing richness of activity patterns and thus complexity, is not as relevant as for the SO regime. It is probably the case that the intense firing of neurogliaform neurons necessary for the activation of GABA_B-Rs is more commonly achieved in synchronized than in asynchronous states (for a review see Craig and McBain 2014; Sanchez-Vives et al. 2020).

Local network excitability, bistability, and the integration–segregation balance in brain slices

A straightforward explanation of our observation of increased sPCI during “awake-like” states is that the sPCI merely reflects network excitability. In other words, the sPCI scored higher just because bath-application of modulators such as CCh or NE increased the excitability of the slice. However, if that were the case, any experimental manipulation

increasing the excitability of the slice would result in higher sPCI values compared to those obtained under the SO regime. (Barbero-Castillo et al., 2019; D'Andola et al., 2017) already demonstrated the opposite, showing that either bath-application of a glutamate receptor agonist (kainate) or electric field modulation (respectively) in cortical slices increased network excitability without affecting sPCI. Finally, the authors did not find a relationship between network excitability and sPCI (D'Andola et al., 2017). Here we further explored the relationship between excitability, inhibition and connectivity in our experiments and computer model and provided a number of novel insights. On one hand, the progressive reduction of fast inhibition gradually increased the firing rate as illustrated in the figures, even leading to epileptiform discharges in some cases. We found that excessive excitability can in fact reduce the sPCI, and statistical analysis indicated that following GABA_ARs blockade, the sPCI was significantly reduced while the relative firing rate increased. On the other hand, GABA_B-R blockade also reduced the sPCI without significantly increasing the firing rate, supporting the idea of the independence of firing rates or excitability and complexity.

Finally, our computer model allowed us to investigate areas of the parameter space that were not visited experimentally. Our model, based on (Compte et al., 2003), reproduced well the experimental results for both spontaneous activity under the different conditions, as well as activity following perturbation. In the model we explored parametrically the variation of GABA_A-R blockade and found the rate of decrease of sPCI reached a minimum for about a 25% decrease in inhibition. Interestingly, we could also enhance inhibition, and found that there is a window of excitatory/inhibitory balance—around the physiological values—in which complexity is maximal, but either enhancing or decreasing inhibitions diminishes complexity. However, when we look at the spatial patterns (Supplementary Information video) we can see how the spatiotemporal pattern to reach decreased complexity can be very different, from a highly disaggregated activity in enhanced inhibition, to hypersynchronization, in low inhibition. This finding bridges the activity of receptors with the activation of the network at the mesocortical level and connects circuit properties with large-scale causal interactions in the cortical network.

Materials and Methods

Slice preparation

Ferrets were treated in accordance with the European Union guidelines on protection of vertebrates used for experimentation (Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the council of 22 September 2010). All experiments were approved by the local ethics committee. Ferrets (4–10 mo., either sex) were deeply anesthetized with isoflurane and sodium pentobarbital (40 mg/kg) before decapitation. The brain was quickly removed and placed in an ice-cold sucrose solution containing (in mM): 213 sucrose, 2.5 KCl, 1 NaH₂PO₄, 26 NaHCO₃, 1 CaCl₂, 3 MgSO₄ and 10 glucose. Acute coronal slices (400- μ m-thick) of the occipital cortex containing visual cortical areas 17, 18, and 19 from both hemispheres were cut with a Microm HM 650V vibratome (Thermo Scientific).

Slices were placed in an interface style recording chamber (Fine Science Tools, Foster City, CA) and superfused with an equal mixture of the above-mentioned sucrose solution and artificial cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF) containing (in mM): 126 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 1 NaH₂PO₄, 26 NaHCO₃, 2 CaCl₂, 2 MgSO₄ and 10 glucose. Next, slices were bathed with ACSF during 1–2 h to allow for recovery. For the slow oscillatory activity to spontaneously emerge, slices were superfused for at least 30 minutes before experiments with ACSF containing (in mM): 126 NaCl, 4 KCl, 1 NaH₂PO₄, 26 NaHCO₃, 1 CaCl₂, 1 MgSO₄ and 10 glucose as in (Sanchez-Vives & McCormick, 2000). All solutions were saturated with carbogen (95% O₂/5% CO₂) to a final pH of 7.4 at 34°C.

In addition to the slow oscillation condition, we used two more experimental conditions that were achieved as follows: (1) “CCh + NE” cholinergic and noradrenergic agonists), by bath-applying a mixture of modulators such as carbachol (CCh, 0.5 μ M) and noradrenaline (NE, 50 μ M). This solution blocks the generation of slow oscillations (D’Andola et al., 2017) but induces a synchronization in a higher frequency of \sim 2 Hz (see below; and see Compte et al., 2008); (2) “awake-like”, asynchronous activity: to achieve a larger degree of asynchrony that better mimics the awake state, we used the same neuromodulators, carbachol (CCh, 0.5 μ M) and noradrenaline (NE, 50 μ M), but additionally we decreased the temperature to 32°C. In a previous study, we found that decreasing the temperature to 32° induced a desynchronization of the network (Reig et al., 2010), which abandoned the bistable Up and Down states regime. Further, we followed Markram et al. (2015) who reduced extracellular calcium in order to switch from

synchronous to asynchronous dynamics. To achieve this, we reduced calcium in the bath from 1–1.2 mM (Sanchez-Vives & McCormick, 2000) to 0.8–0.9 mM. These manipulations led to a rather asynchronous pattern of activity which we termed “awake-like state” (Figure 2A–C).

Electrophysiological recordings

We recorded the extracellular local field potential (LFP) using a 16-channel SU-8-based flexible microarray (Capone et al., 2019; Illa et al., 2015). Care was taken to distribute the recording electrodes in supra and infragranular layers as shown in Figure 1A. Signals were amplified by 100 using a PGA16 Multichannel System (Multichannel Systems MCS GmbH-Harvard Bioscience Inc, Reutlingen, Germany). LFPs were digitized with a Power 1401 or 1401 mkII CED interface (Cambridge Electronic Design, Cambridge, UK) at a sampling rate of 5 or 10 kHz and acquired with Spike2 software (Cambridge Electronic Design, Cambridge, UK).

Pharmacological agents

Carbachol (CCh) and norepinephrine (NE) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. For the block of GABA_A receptors we used bicuculline methiodide (BMI: 0.2 μM, 0.4 μM, 0.6 μM, 0.8 μM and 1 μM), obtained from Tocris Bioscience; and SR-95531 hydrobromide (gabazine, GBZ 50 nM, 100 nM, 150 nM and 200 nM), obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. We also progressively blocked slow inhibition (GABA_B receptors) by means of CGP 55845 (CGP100 nM, 200 nM, 500 nM and 1 μM), obtained from Tocris Bioscience

Network dynamics analysis during spontaneous activity

For every condition tested, we analyzed 300 s of spontaneous activity (no electrical stimulation pulses). We first estimated multi-unit activity (MUA) from LFP recordings and detected Up and Down states as previously described (D’Andola et al., 2017; Reig et al., 2010; Ruiz-Mejias et al., 2016). Briefly, the MUA signal was calculated as the average power of the normalized spectra at high-frequency band (200–1500 Hz), since power variations in the Fourier components at high frequencies of LFP provide a reliable estimate of the population firing rate (Mattia & Del Giudice, 2002). The MUA signal was then logarithmically scaled to balance large fluctuations of nearby spikes. We detected Up and Down states setting duration and amplitude thresholds in the log(MUA) signal.

In this way, we could compute different parameters that characterize SO, such as oscillation frequency or Up and Down state durations.

The firing rate was calculated as the peak $\log(\text{MUA})$ value during Up states normalized by the $\log(\text{MUA})$ during Down states. The complexity of the $\log(\text{MUA})$ time series was obtained by computing Sample Entropy (SampEn). SampEn (m, r, N) is the negative natural logarithm of the conditional probability that two sequences of length N , similar for m points, remain similar, that is, within a tolerance r , at the next point, where self-matches are not included in calculating the probability (Richman & Moorman, 2000). Following previous studies (Sokunbi et al., 2013), we chose $m=2$ and $r=0.25$.

PCI for *in vitro* recordings (sPCI)

In order to estimate perturbational complexity in brain slices, we used an adaptation of the PCI used in humans (Casali et al., 2013), named sPCI (D'Andola et al., 2017). The stimulation electrode was placed in infragranular layers (Figure 1A). Pulses had a duration of 0.1 ms, an intensity of 150–200 μA , and were applied every 10 s, with a random jitter from 0.5 to 1.5 s to avoid activity entrainment to the specific frequency of stimulation (Figure 1B). A binary spatiotemporal distribution of significant activity was calculated in the MUA signal: we assessed the statistical differences between the network activity baseline and its response to the electrical stimulation using a bootstrap procedure as in D'Andola et al. (2017). The significance threshold was estimated as the one-tail ($1-\alpha$) 99th percentile of the bootstrap distribution. Also, we first low-pass filtered ($<10\text{Hz}$) the trial average computed on the MUA signal, and considered significant only the periods in which the activity of each channel lay above the significance threshold for more than 50 ms. The sPCI was then defined as the normalized Lempel–Ziv complexity of the binary matrix of significant evoked MUA spatiotemporal patterns (D'Andola et al., 2017). Furthermore, we computed the temporal evolution of the sPCI, the sPCI(t), performing the calculation of the index in temporal windows of increasing duration after the stimulation (D'Andola et al., 2017).

Experimental design and statistical analysis

Data are reported as mean \pm SEM. Statistical significance was assessed using one-way repeated-measures ANOVA with post-hoc Tukey's test to identify significant interactions. Exact p values are reported throughout the text and were considered significant when $p<0.05$. Mauchly's test was used to assess the sphericity assumption in

ANOVA. In data sets containing relative firing rate measurements, the Greenhouse–Geisser procedure was applied to correct for violations of sphericity. All data analyses were performed using either MATLAB (Mathworks, Natick, MA) or Origin 8 Pro (OriginLabCorportation, Northampton, MA).

Computational modeling

The model consists of a two-dimensional 50×50 squared network of pyramidal cells (80%) and interneurons (20%), randomly distributed and interconnected through biologically plausible synaptic dynamics. Each cell is sparsely and locally connected to its neighbors within a square of size $L \times L$ centered around it, where $L_{\text{pyramidal}}=7$ and $L_{\text{interneuron}}=5$. The fraction of synaptic connections (outgoing synapses) is set at 50% for pyramidal cells and 90% for interneurons, of the total number of neurons within the local range, thus imposing local connections for interneurons and more sparse connections for pyramidal cells (see Figure 7A). The network structure is similar to that used in previous studies of oscillatory neuronal networks (Bazhenov et al., 2008; Dalla Porta & Copelli, 2019; Poil et al., 2012). The neuron model and its ion channel dynamics are borrowed with maximal conductance adjustment from (Compte et al., 2003). Additionally, the model accounts for the potassium leak current I_{KL} , which is modulated by acetylcholine and norepinephrine (Bazhenov et al., 2002; Li et al., 2017) and by GABA_B inhibitory synapses. Briefly, the pyramidal cells, consisting in a somatic and a dendritic compartment, are modeled as:

$$C_m A_s \frac{dV_s}{dt} = -A_s (I_L + I_{KL} + I_{Na} + I_K + I_A + I_{KS} + I_{KNa}) - I_{syn,i} - g_{sd} (V_s - V_d), \quad (1)$$

and,

$$C_m A_d \frac{dV_d}{dt} = -A_d (I_L + I_{Ca} + I_{KCa} + I_{NaP} + I_{AR}) - I_{syn,E} - g_{sd} (V_d - V_s). \quad (2)$$

Where v_s and V_d represent the soma and dendrite voltage, respectively. C_m is the specific membrane capacitance, g_{sd} is the conductance of the electrical coupling between soma and dendrite, and A_s and A_d are the membrane areas of soma and dendrite, respectively. The soma includes the following channels and respective maximal conductances (g): leakage current (I_L , $g_L=0.0667 \pm 0.0067 \text{ mS/cm}^2$), potassium leakage current (I_{KL} , $g_{KL}=1.86 \text{ mS/cm}^2$), sodium current (I_{Na} , $g_{Na}=50 \text{ mS/cm}^2$), potassium current (I_K , $g_K=10.5 \text{ mS/cm}^2$), A-type K^+ current (I_A , $g_A=0.95 \text{ mS/cm}^2$), non-inactivating slow K^+

current (I_{KS} , $g_{KS}=0.5472$ mS/cm²) and the Na⁺-dependent K⁺ current (I_{KNa} , $g_{KNa}=0.65835$ mS/cm²). The dendrite includes: leakage current (I_L , $g_L=0.0667\pm 0.0067$ mS/cm²), high-threshold Ca²⁺ channel (I_{Ca} , $g_{Ca}=0.43$ mS/cm²), Ca²⁺-dependent K⁺ current (I_{KCa} , $g_{KCa}=0.5415$ mS/cm²), persistent Na⁺ channel (I_{NaP} , $g_{NaP}=0.05145$ mS/cm²) and the anomalous rectifier K⁺ channel (I_{AR} , $g_{AR}=0.0257$ mS/cm²). $I_{syn,I}$ and $I_{syn,E}$ are the inhibitory and excitatory synaptic currents, respectively. The interneurons, consisting in only one compartment, are simply modeled as:

$$C_m A_i \frac{dV_s}{dt} = -A_i (I_L + I_{Na} + I_K) - I_{syn}, \quad (3)$$

where A_i is the total membrane area and I_{syn} accounts for both the inhibitory and excitatory synaptic currents. All the details of the implementation of these currents are described by (Compte et al., 2003), except for I_{KL} and $GABA_B$, that are described below. The $GABA_B$ current (I_{GABAB}) was modeled as (Destexhe et al., 1996; Liu et al., 2019):

$$I_{GABAB} = g_{GABAB} \frac{s^4}{s^4 + K_d} (V - V_{GABAB}), \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = 0.5T(1 - r) - 0.0012r, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = 0.18r - 0.034s, \quad (6)$$

where r and s represent the $GABA_B$ receptor and the gating variable, respectively. The transmitter concentration T is modeled as a square pulse of 0.5 mM during 3 ms. I_{KL} is modeled as in (Li et al., 2017) where $I_{KL}=g_{KL}(V-V_K)$, with $V_K=-100$ mV (potassium reversal potential). The synaptic maximal conductances (g_x^{jk} , where x stands for AMPA, NDMA, $GABA_A$ and $GABA_B$, and j and k stand for the presynaptic and postsynaptic neuron, respectively) are set to the following values: $g_{AMPA}^{EE}=6.2$ nS, $g_{AMPA}^{EI}=0.6925$ nS, $g_{NMDA}^{EE}=2.72$ nS, $g_{NMDA}^{EI}=0.595$ nS, $g_{GABAA}^{II}=1.96$ nS, $g_{GABAA}^{IE}=28.96$ nS, $g_{GABAB}^{II}=33.7$ nS and $g_{GABAB}^{IE}=39.2$ nS, where the I and E, stand for the inhibitory and excitatory neurons. Additionally, all the neurons receive a heterogeneous Poisson train of excitatory presynaptic potentials with a rate of 0.5 kHz. The Poisson synaptic maximal conductances are set in: $g_{AMPA}^E=1.2$ nS, $g_{AMPA}^I=0.4625$ nS, $g_{NMDA}^E=0.4$ nS and $g_{NMDA}^I=0.095$ nS. In order to simulate the experimental effects of $GABA_{A,B}$ blockade, we progressively reduced the $GABA_{A,B}$ channel conductances (which will be referred to as simple concentration) in inhibitory synapses to both neurons, pyramidal and interneurons, from 5% to 90%. We proceeded in the same way in order to progressively increase the

GABA_A channel conductance in Figure 8B, increasing it from 5% to 90%. For the stimuli procedure, we depolarized all the neurons by a brief external stimulation of 0.5 nA during 40 ms with an interval of stimulation of 5 ± 1 s (mean \pm SD given). The simulated population membrane potential (sLFP) was computed as the sum of the absolute values of the excitatory and inhibitory synaptic currents acting on the excitatory neurons (San Cristóbal et al., 2016). We virtually created 12 electrodes in the model, arranged as a 4 \times 3 matrix. Each electrode covered an area of 49 neurons and were horizontally and vertically spaced by a distance of 10 neurons, thus ensuring no overlapping between electrodes. The neurons on the border were not considered. The model was implemented in a C code and simulated using a fourth-order Runge–Kutta method with a time step of 0.06 ms during 210 s. To compute the mean response of the membrane potential we averaged over 10 realizations of the external noise, network connectivity and neuron parameters.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Alkire, M. T., Hudetz, A. G., & Tononi, G. (2008). Consciousness and anesthesia. *Science (New York, NY)*, 322(322), 876–880. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1149213>. Consciousness
- Andalman, A. S., Burns, V. M., Lovett-Barron, M., Broxton, M., Poole, B., Yang, S. J., Grosenick, L., Lerner, T. N., Chen, R., Benster, T., Mourrain, P., Levoy, M., Rajan, K., & Deisseroth, K. (2019). Neuronal Dynamics Regulating Brain and Behavioral State Transitions. *Cell*, 177(4), 970–985.e20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2019.02.037>
- Arena, A., Comolatti, R., Thon, S., Casali, A. G., & Storm, J. F. (2020). General anaesthesia disrupts complex cortical dynamics in response to intracranial electrical stimulation in rats. *BioRxiv*, 2020.02.25.964056. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.25.964056>
- Barbero-Castillo, A., Weinert, J. F., Camassa, A., Perez-Mendez, L., Caldas-Martinez, S., Mattia, M., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2019). Proceedings #31: Cortical Network Complexity under Different Levels of Excitability Controlled by Electric Fields. *Brain Stimulation*, 12(2), e97–e99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BRS.2018.12.200>
- Bazhenov, M., Rulkov, N. F., & Timofeev, I. (2008). Effect of synaptic connectivity on long-range synchronization of fast cortical oscillations. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, 100(3), 1562–1575. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.90613.2008>
- Bazhenov, Maxim, Timofeev, I., Steriade, M., & Sejnowski, T. J. (2002). Model of thalamocortical slow-wave sleep oscillations and transitions to activated states. *Journal of Neuroscience*, 22(19), 8691–

8704. <https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.22-19-08691.2002>
- Bettinardi, R. G., Tort-Colet, N., Ruiz-Mejias, M., Sanchez-Vives, M. V., & Deco, G. (2015). Gradual emergence of spontaneous correlated brain activity during fading of general anesthesia in rats: Evidences from fMRI and local field potentials. *NeuroImage, 114*, 185–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.03.037>
- Brumberg, J. C., Nowak, L. G., & McCormick, D. A. (2000). Ionic mechanisms underlying repetitive high-frequency burst firing in supragranular cortical neurons. *Journal of Neuroscience, 20*(13), 4829–4843. <https://doi.org/10.1523/jneurosci.20-13-04829.2000>
- Bullmore, E., & Sporns, O. (2009). Complex brain networks: graph theoretical analysis of structural and functional systems. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience, 10*(3), 186–198. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn2575>
- Capone, C., Rebollo, B., Muñoz, A., Illa, X., Del Giudice, P., Sanchez-Vives, M. V., Mattia, M., Munoz, A., Illa, X., Giudice, P. Del, Sanchez-Vives, M. V., & Mattia, M. (2019). Slow Waves in Cortical Slices: How Spontaneous Activity is Shaped by Laminar Structure. *Cerebral Cortex, 29*(1), 319–335. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhx326>
- Casali, A. G., Gosseries, O., Rosanova, M., Boly, M., Sarasso, S., Casali, K. R., Casarotto, S., Bruno, M.-A., Laureys, S., Tononi, G., & Massimini, M. (2013). A theoretically based index of consciousness independent of sensory processing and behavior. *Science Translational Medicine, 5*(198), 198ra105. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.3006294>
- Casarotto, S., Comanducci, A., Rosanova, M., Sarasso, S., Fecchio, M., Napolitani, M., Pigorini, A., G. Casali, A., Trimarchi, P. D., Boly, M., Gosseries, O., Bodart, O., Curto, F., Landi, C., Mariotti, M., Devalle, G., Laureys, S., Tononi, G., & Massimini, M. (2016). Stratification of unresponsive patients by an independently validated index of brain complexity. *Annals of Neurology, 80*(5), 718–729. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ana.24779>
- Chauvette, S., Crochet, S., Volgushev, M., & Timofeev, I. (2011). Properties of Slow Oscillation during Slow-Wave Sleep and Anesthesia in Cats. *Journal of Neuroscience, 31*(42), 14998–15008. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2339-11.2011>
- Chen, Y., Anand, S., Martinez-Conde, S., Macknik, S. L., Bereshpolova, Y., Swadlow, H. A., & Alonso, J. M. (2009). The linearity and selectivity of neuronal responses in awake visual cortex. *Journal of Vision, 9*(9), 12–12. <https://doi.org/10.1167/9.9.12>
- Comolatti, R., Pigorini, A., Casarotto, S., Fecchio, M., Faria, G., Sarasso, S., Rosanova, M., Gosseries, O., Boly, M., Bodart, O., Ledoux, D., Brichant, J.-F. F., Nobili, L., Laureys, S., Tononi, G., Massimini, M., & Casali, A. G. (2019). A fast and general method to empirically estimate the complexity of brain responses to transcranial and intracranial stimulations. *Brain Stimulation, (in press)*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brs.2019.05.013>
- Compte, A., Reig, R., Descalzo, V. F., Harvey, M. A., Puccini, G. D., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2008). Spontaneous high-frequency (10–80 Hz) oscillations during up states in the cerebral cortex in vitro. *The Journal of Neuroscience : The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience, 28*(51), 13828–13844. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2684-08.2008>
- Compte, A., Sanchez-Vives, M. V., McCormick, D. A., & Wang, X.-J. (2003). Cellular and network mechanisms of slow oscillatory activity. *Journal of Neurophysiology, 89*(5), 2707–2725. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00845.2002>
- Constantinople, C. M., Bruno, R. M., Kock, C. P. de, Kuner, T., Sakmann, B., Carandini, M., Lu, J., & Lecea, L. de. (2011). Effects and mechanisms of wakefulness on local cortical networks. *Neuron, 69*(6), 1061–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2011.02.040>
- Craig, M. T., & McBain, C. J. (2014). The emerging role of GABAB receptors as regulators of network dynamics: fast actions from a ‘slow’ receptor? *Current Opinion in Neurobiology, 0*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONB.2013.10.002>
- D’Andola, M., Rebollo, B., Casali, A. G., Weinert, J. F., Pigorini, A., Villa, R., Massimini, M., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2017). Bistability, Causality, and Complexity in Cortical Networks: An In Vitro Perturbational Study. *Cerebral Cortex, 91*(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhx122>
- Dalla Porta, L., & Copelli, M. (2019). Modeling neuronal avalanches and long-range temporal correlations at the emergence of collective oscillations: Continuously varying exponents mimic M/EEG results. *PLoS Computational Biology, 15*(4), e1006924. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1006924>
- Destexhe, A., Bal, T., McCormick, D. A., & Sejnowski, T. J. (1996). Ionic mechanisms underlying synchronized oscillations and propagating waves in a model of ferret thalamic slices. *Journal of Neurophysiology, 76*(3), 2049–2070. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.1996.76.3.2049>
- Duarte, R., Seeholzer, A., Zilles, K., & Morrison, A. (2017). Synaptic patterning and the timescales of cortical dynamics. *Current Opinion in Neurobiology, 43*, 156–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONB.2017.02.007>

- Giacino, J. T., Fins, J. J., Laureys, S., & Schiff, N. D. (2014). Disorders of consciousness after acquired brain injury: the state of the science. *Nature Reviews Neurology*, *10*(2), 99–114. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrneurol.2013.279>
- Hobson, J. A., & Pace-Schott, E. F. (2002). The cognitive neuroscience of sleep: neuronal systems, consciousness and learning. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, *3*(9), 679–693. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn915>
- Hudetz, A. G. (2012). General Anesthesia and Human Brain Connectivity. *Brain Connectivity*, *2*(6), 291. <https://doi.org/10.1089/BRAIN.2012.0107>
- Hudetz, A. G., Liu, X., Pillay, S., Boly, M., & Tononi, G. (2016). Propofol anesthesia reduces Lempel-Ziv complexity of spontaneous brain activity in rats. *Neuroscience Letters*, *628*, 132–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEULET.2016.06.017>
- Illa, X., Rebollo, B., Gabriel, G., Sánchez-Vives, M. V. M. V., & Villa, R. (2015). A SU-8-based flexible microprobe for close and distal recordings from the cortical network. In S. van den Driesche (Ed.), *Progress in Biomedical Optics and Imaging - Proceedings of SPIE* (Vol. 9518, p. 951803). International Society for Optics and Photonics. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2180454>
- Isaacson, J., & Scanziani, M. (2011). How Inhibition Shapes Cortical Activity. *Neuron*, *72*(2), 231–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2011.09.027>
- Jones, B. E. (2005). From waking to sleeping: neuronal and chemical substrates. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences*, *26*(11), 578–586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tips.2005.09.009>
- Khawaled, R., Bruening-Wright, A., Adelman, J. P., & Maylie, J. (1999). Bicuculline block of small-conductance calcium-activated potassium channels. *Pflügers Archiv European Journal of Physiology*, *438*(3), 314–321. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004240050915>
- Li, G., Henriquez, C. S., & Fröhlich, F. (2017). Unified thalamic model generates multiple distinct oscillations with state-dependent entrainment by stimulation. *PLOS Computational Biology*, *13*(10), e1005797. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005797>
- Liu, Y., Milton, J., & Campbell, S. A. (2019). Outgrowing seizures in Childhood Absence Epilepsy: time delays and bistability. *Journal of Computational Neuroscience*, *46*, 197–209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10827-019-00711-x>
- Mann, E. O., Kohl, M. M., & Paulsen, O. (2009). Distinct roles of GABA(A) and GABA(B) receptors in balancing and terminating persistent cortical activity. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *29*(23), 7513–7518. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.6162-08.2009>
- Markram, H., Muller, E., Ramaswamy, S., Reimann, M. W., Abdellah, M., Sanchez, C. A., Ailamaki, A., Alonso-Nanclares, L., Antille, N., Arsever, S., Kahou, G. A. A., Berger, T. K., Bilgili, A., Buncic, N., Chalimourda, A., Chindemi, G., Courcol, J.-D., Delalondre, F., Delattre, V., ... Schürmann, F. (2015). Reconstruction and Simulation of Neocortical Microcircuitry. *Cell*, *163*(2), 456–492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2015.09.029>
- Massimini, M., Huber, R., Ferrarelli, F., Hill, S., & Tononi, G. (2004). The SSO as a Traveling Wave. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *24*(31), 6862–6870. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1318-04.2004>
- Massimini, Marcello, Ferrarelli, F., Esser, S. K., Riedner, B. A., Huber, R., Murphy, M., Peterson, M. J., & Tononi, G. (2007). Triggering sleep slow waves by transcranial magnetic stimulation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0702495104>
- Massimini, Marcello, Ferrarelli, F., Huber, R., Esser, S. K., Singh, H., & Tononi, G. (2005). Breakdown of cortical effective connectivity during sleep. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, *309*(5744), 2228–2232. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1117256>
- Mattia, M., & Del Giudice, P. (2002). Population dynamics of interacting spiking neurons [Journal Article]. *Phys Rev E Stat Nonlin Soft Matter Phys*, *66*(5 Pt 1), 51917. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.66.051917>
- McCormick, D. A. (1992). Neurotransmitter actions in the thalamus and cerebral cortex and their role in neuromodulation of thalamocortical activity. *Progress in Neurobiology*, *39*(4), 337–388. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-0082\(92\)90012-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0301-0082(92)90012-4)
- McCormick, D. A., Nestvogel, D. B., & He, B. J. (2020). Neuromodulation of Brain State and Behavior. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*, *43*(1), annurev-neuro-100219-105424. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-neuro-100219-105424>
- Perez-Zabalza, M., Reig, R., Manrique, J., Jercog, D., Winograd, M., Parga, N., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2020). Modulation of cortical slow oscillatory rhythm by GABA B receptors: an in vitro experimental and computational study. *The Journal of Physiology*, JP279476. <https://doi.org/10.1113/JP279476>
- Pigorini, A., Sarasso, S., Proserpio, P., Szymanski, C., Arnulfo, G., Casarotto, S., Fecchio, M., Rosanova, M., Mariotti, M., Lo Russo, G., Palva, J. M., Nobili, L., & Massimini, M. (2015). Bistability

- breaks-off deterministic responses to intracortical stimulation during non-REM sleep. *NeuroImage*, *112*, 105–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2015.02.056>
- Poil, S. S., Hardstone, R., Mansvelder, H. D., & Linkenkaer-Hansen, K. (2012). Critical-state dynamics of avalanches and oscillations jointly emerge from balanced excitation/inhibition in neuronal networks. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *32*(29), 9817–9823. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5990-11.2012>
- Poulet, J. F. A., & Crochet, S. (2019). The cortical states of wakefulness. In *Frontiers in Systems Neuroscience* (Vol. 12). Frontiers Media S.A. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnsys.2018.00064>
- Reig, R., Mattia, M., Compte, A., Belmonte, C., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2010). Temperature Modulation of Slow and Fast Cortical Rhythms. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, *103*(3), 1253–1261. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00890.2009>
- Richman, J. S., & Moorman, J. R. (2000). Physiological time-series analysis using approximate and sample entropy. *American Journal of Physiology - Heart and Circulatory Physiology*, *278* (6), H2039–H2049. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.2000.278.6.h2039>
- Riedner, B. A., Vyazovskiy, V. V., Huber, R., Massimini, M., Esser, S., Murphy, M., & Tononi, G. (2007). Sleep homeostasis and cortical synchronization: III. A high-density EEG study of sleep slow waves in humans. *Sleep*, *30*(12), 1643–1657.
- Rosanova, M., Fecchio, M., Casarotto, S., Sarasso, S., Casali, A. G., Pigorini, A., Comanducci, A., Seregini, F., Devalle, G., Citerio, G., Bodart, O., Boly, M., Gosseries, O., Laureys, S., & Massimini, M. (2018). Sleep-like cortical OFF-periods disrupt causality and complexity in the brain of unresponsive wakefulness syndrome patients. *Nature Communications*, *9*(1), 4427. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-06871-1>
- Rosanova, Mario, Gosseries, O., Casarotto, S., Boly, M., Casali, A. G., Bruno, M.-A., Mariotti, M., Boveroux, P., Tononi, G., Laureys, S., & Massimini, M. (2012). Recovery of cortical effective connectivity and recovery of consciousness in vegetative patients. *Brain*, *135*(4), 1308–1320. <https://doi.org/10.1093/brain/awr340>
- Ruiz-Mejias, M., Martinez de Lagran, M., Mattia, M., Castano-Prat, P., Perez-Mendez, L., Ciria-Suarez, L., Gener, T., Sancristobal, B., García-Ojalvo, J., Gruart, A., Delgado-García, J. M., Sanchez-Vives, M. V., & Dierssen, M. (2016). Overexpression of Dyrk1A, a Down Syndrome Candidate, Decreases Excitability and Impairs Gamma Oscillations in the Prefrontal Cortex. *The Journal of Neuroscience : The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, *36*(13), 3648–3659. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2517-15.2016>
- Sanchez-Vives, M. V., Barbero-Castillo, A., Perez-Zabalza, M., & Reig, R. (2020). GABAB receptor-modulation of thalamocortical dynamics and synaptic plasticity. *Neuroscience*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.NEUROSCIENCE.2020.03.011>
- Sanchez-Vives, M. V., & Mattia, M. (2014). Slow wave activity as the default mode of the cerebral cortex. *Arch Ital Biol*, *152*, 2–3. <https://doi.org/10.12871/000298292014239>
- Sanchez-Vives, M. V., & McCormick, D. A. (2000). Cellular and network mechanisms of rhythmic recurrent activity in neocortex. *Nature Neuroscience*, *3*(10), 1027–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1038/79848>
- Sanchez-Vives, M. V., Mattia, M., Compte, A., Perez-Zabalza, M., Winograd, M., Descalzo, V. F., & Reig, R. (2010). Inhibitory modulation of cortical up states. *J. Neurophysiol.*, *104*(3), 1314–1324. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.00178.2010>
- Sancristóbal, B., Rebollo, B., Boada, P., Sanchez-Vives, M. V., & Garcia-Ojalvo, J. (2016). Collective stochastic coherence in recurrent neuronal networks. *Nature Physics*, *12*(9), 881–887. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nphys3739>
- Sarasso, S., Boly, M., Napolitani, M., Gosseries, O., Charland-Verville, V., Casarotto, S., Rosanova, M., Casali, A. G., Brichant, J. F., Boveroux, P., Rex, S., Tononi, G., Laureys, S., & Massimini, M. (2015). Consciousness and complexity during unresponsiveness induced by propofol, xenon, and ketamine. *Current Biology*, *25*(23), 3099–3105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2015.10.014>
- Scammell, T. E., Arrigoni, E., & Lipton, J. O. (2017). Neural Circuitry of Wakefulness and Sleep. *Neuron*, *93*(4), 747–765. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2017.01.014>
- Sokunbi, M. O., Fung, W., Sawlani, V., Choppin, S., Linden, D. E. J., & Thome, J. (2013). Resting state fMRI entropy probes complexity of brain activity in adults with ADHD. *Psychiatry Research - Neuroimaging*, *214*(3), 341–348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2013.10.001>
- Steriade, M., Contreras, D., Curró Dossi, R., Nuñez, A., Houtkooper, R. H., Auwerx, J., Franken, P., & Tafti, M. (1993). The slow (< 1 Hz) oscillation in reticular thalamic and thalamocortical neurons: scenario of sleep rhythm generation in interacting thalamic and neocortical networks. *The Journal of Neuroscience : The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience*, *13*(8), 3284–3299. <https://doi.org/11124996>

- Steriade, M., Timofeev, I., & Grenier, F. (2001). Natural waking and sleep states: a view from inside neocortical neurons. *Journal of Neurophysiology*, *85*(5), 1969–1985. <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.2001.85.5.1969>
- Szczepański, J., Amigó, J. M., Wajnryb, E., & Sanchez-Vives, M. V. (2003). Application of Lempel–Ziv complexity to the analysis of neural discharges. *Network: Computation in Neural Systems*, *14*(2), 335–350. https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-898X_14_2_309
- Tononi, G., & Edelman, G. M. (1998). Consciousness and complexity. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, *282*(5395), 1846–1851. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.282.5395.1846>
- Tononi, Giulio, Sporns, O., & Edelman, G. M. (1994). A measure for brain complexity: Relating functional segregation and integration in the nervous system. *Neurobiology*, *91*, 5033–5037. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.91.11.5033>
- Varley, T. F., Luppi, A. I., Pappas, I., Naci, L., Adapa, R., Owen, A. M., Menon, D. K., & Stamatakis, E. A. (2020). Consciousness & Brain Functional Complexity in Propofol Anaesthesia. *Scientific Reports*, *10*(1), 1018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-57695-3>
- Weber, F., & Dan, Y. (2016). Circuit-based interrogation of sleep control. *Nature*, *538*(7623), 51–59. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature19773>
- Zamora-López, G., Chen, Y., Deco, G., Kringelbach, M. L., & Zhou, C. (2016). Functional complexity emerging from anatomical constraints in the brain: The significance of network modularity and rich-clubs. *Scientific Reports*, *6*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep38424>
- Zhao, M., Qiu, W. ., & Liu, B. . (2010). Relative entropy evaluation method for multiple attribute decision making. *Control and Decision*, *25*(7), 1098–1100.